

Reflection on E-Learning and Adaptability in the Teaching and Learning of French as Foreign Language

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 23 May 2022	The teaching of French in Morocco has seen better days. "A progressive and almost generalized decline in the level of French throughout the Moroccan school curriculum is certainly not original" [1]. The secondary cycle is one of them. Today, it encounters several difficulties that cannot be neglected. This is due to the learning methods or approaches as well as the programs imposed by the institutions and which do not take into consideration the expectations of the actors involved in the educational act especially with the integration of literary works. The learner, with a mostly low level, due to the accumulation of different factors, is disoriented, demotivated and gradually detaches himself from the learning of this language. In this light, we must look for other approaches and pedagogical methods to improve the quality of teaching/learning of French at the qualifying secondary level through the use of ICT and the adaptation of training which constitutes a new challenge in the field.
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I. INTRODUCTION

The world is evolving faster than we think and the socio-economic environments are constantly changing. Institutions are not only called upon to adapt, but they have an interest in doing so quickly and efficiently. However, change is not an easy phenomenon, especially when it comes to the introduction of ICT, because the latter is a key element and increasingly affects organizational and pedagogical practices. Our research is part of the general framework of language didactics. It is a question of reflecting on language learning, especially FLE. At a time when the use of information and communication technologies for teaching (ICTE) is expanding and pedagogical platforms are multiplying, a remarkable challenge corroborates this reflection, that is the integration of these technologies (ICTE) in the teaching and learning of French as a foreign language. This integration becomes a real pedagogical challenge.

More specifically, in this research work, we will extend the reflection on an area that arouses the interest of several researchers; that of the use of a new type of teaching/learning in a basic training in Morocco whose main objective is to improve the quality of the teaching of literary works in the qualifying secondary cycle by changing the approaches and by integrating technology. It is a question of carrying out a research on the use of the TICE to propose mediated tasks

within the framework of the action-oriented perspective privileged by the CECR. Our problematic is based on the following questioning:

If ICTE are part of the pedagogical tools available in schools, are teachers and learners able to use them to carry out tasks and reach actional objectives? And on the other hand, how can the adaptation of courses and training motivate the learner and make him master of his learning?

From all these questions emerge a certain number of hypotheses that we can describe as follows:

- ICT, a highly motivating tool for the language classroom, would allow the learner to act and contribute to his own learning.
- Today's learners are veritable Internet users, which is why learning French through the Internet would interest and motivate them.
- With the resources available, it is possible to provide learners or groups of learners with an authentic communication environment where they can freely express their autonomy, work in collaboration, take action, share their ideas, complete tasks and develop learning strategies.

II. INTEGRATION OF ICTE IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

This is how C. Bourguignon defines integration: "By integration, we mean any insertion of the technological tool, during one or more sessions, in a global pedagogical sequence, whose objectives have been clearly determined. For each phase, the modalities of realization are explained in terms of prerequisites, objects, progress of the task, evaluation, so that the whole constitutes a coherent didactic device "[2]. For Mangenot " The integration (of ICTE) is when the computer tool is used with efficiency at the service of learning "[3].

From this perspective, it is quite clear that information and communication technologies for education (ICTE) offer a very interesting opportunity to modernize education systems. This interest is the result of the fact that ICTE allows for the diversification of objectives, methods, materials, projects and learning outcomes. But they require a rigorous approach that allows the renovation of pedagogical practices.

To demonstrate the value of this integration in the classroom, several studies seek to prove that learners show a higher level of motivation for a learning activity that uses ICT than for the usual approaches in the classroom. The initial results lead us to confirm that the digital workspace in general promotes pedagogical support and continuity by creating more motivating and meaningful learning. Today, we can see that the technological evolution is such that it simply makes it impossible for students to be passive in front of the screens. They contribute to create their own documents and build skills: accessibility of information, exchange of e-mails, consultation of documentary sources, communication and exchange in real time or deferred with learning communities, interactivity...

According to these important and recognized benefits of the use of ICT, Merieu affirms that: "Everyone may find a situation where he can appropriate the knowledge proposed" [4]. The learner, closely linked to the availability of the material and its accessibility, advances at his own rhythm and is freed from several constraints such as time, pressure and the comparison of his performance with his peers. As a result, we are witnessing an autonomy. For Mangenot, the concept of autonomy, widely used in the field of learning, means: "autonomous work in front of a computer" [5], referring to the fact that the learner works alone on his computer, without the assistance of his teacher or peers. Thanks to the individualization of learning rhythms, autonomy is made more possible. It is motivating because the learner becomes capable of regulating his own behavior and experience by himself. It is also beneficial because the learner acquires a sense of accomplishing an action effectively through his own abilities.

The introduction of Information and Communication Technologies in the field of education has given rise to a rich jargon:

III. TOWARDS "SOCIAL LEARNING"

Learning in the digital age strongly mobilizes the social dimension. The term "social learning" "first appeared in commercial speeches, conferences, interventions, and consultant blogs"[6].

The idea of social learning is to apply social technologies (social networks, wikis, forums, data bases, community platforms...) for training purposes.

The current social learning is in line with the logic of Web 2.0 where open and interactive technologies are gaining power and allow the (external) integration of new technological tools such as technological supports for example, video capsules. "From now on, with the Internet and the digital civilization, in particular with social networks and the mobile Internet, we see the emergence of new forms of intelligence, an intelligence that could be described as connective, collaborative and collective"[7].

Seen from this angle, social learning is largely inspired by socioconstructivist theories. In the view of Cristol, "it is in the learning communities described by Lave and Wenger¹²⁸ (1991) that we can find the closest connection. For these authors, a community of practice is a social learning system with a structure self-organizing capacity, shifting boundaries and a continuous negotiation of identities and meaning. These communities definitely break with the vision of an isolated brain that is growing, storing and processing ever more information" [8].

A. *E-learning* :

"E-learning", which is at the origin of the notion of social learning, contains the term learning (seen as the personal acquisition of knowledge, skills, attitudes, etc.) [9].

E-learning according to the definition of the European Commission is "the use of new multimedia technologies and the Internet to improve the quality of learning by facilitating access to resources and services, as well as exchanges and collaboration at a distance".

We can also define e-Learning as a tool or a means, dynamized by electronics, among a wide range, used both to facilitate or extend learning and support various forms of teaching. It is thus about consulting documents on the Net to teach in distance learning, as a complement or instead of face-to-face teaching.

B. *Adaptive E-Learning* :

Adaptive systems have become increasingly popular since the early 1990s, and thanks to artificial intelligence and algorithms exploited in the field of education, these systems try to act differently with each student, based on the information accumulated in the student's model.

This is a new approach to training, or rather a new way of learning based on access to online, interactive and sometimes personalized training. This access allows the development of learners' skills, while making the learning process independent of time and place.

The adaptation of distance learning situations is one of the main obstacles in e-learning. The challenge here is to understand the learner's behavior and propose content adapted to his needs. To do this, the adaptation must take into account the evolution of the learner's profile during the learning process. In other terms, the cognitive abilities evolve with the learning process, resulting in the end a content that no longer corresponds to their skills.

In this context of the emergence of technologies and in front of the contributions that they seem to be able to support the system of teaching in general, we propose to treat the questions relating to the contribution of the ICTE in the teaching/learning of the FLE in particular while starting from the approach centered on "the task" and on "the pedagogical scenario".

IV. THE MEDIATED TASK

The educational system seeks to use the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages in the teaching of the French language. The Action-oriented Perspective is recommended in this framework, because "the learner-user is considered as an actor of his learning and a social actor who evolves and acts in a social context. He performs tasks that are not only linguistic in given circumstances and environment, within a particular field of action" [10] In the same way, institutions tend towards the integration and use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in the language teaching/learning process. Mediatization is one of the solutions frequently approved for the development of new teaching and learning modalities. Based on a study made by Catroux, he notes that "there are implications between the new action-oriented perspective and the authentic potentialities of the available ICTs, where the responsibility of social actors can be engaged"[11].

According to Christian Puren, we are moving from communication to co-action by using ICT, particularly Web 2.0. The use of ICT can be easily inserted in activities implemented in the framework of teaching, as "they can be a key element to accomplish tasks or activities of a specifically pedagogical nature based on the "real" social and interactive nature and immediacy of the classroom situation"[12]. Thus, learners can develop language skills from technological tools such as the Internet, blogs and chats outside the classroom because their place in the pedagogical triangle nowadays is not like it was in the past. Constructivism and then cognitivism have revalued the status of the learner by considering him as a real actor of his learning.

The first forms of using ICT in mediated training were strongly influenced by behaviourism in the sense that they proposed activities based on stimulus/response. On the other hand, the new devices are influenced by constructivism in the sense that the learner is not invited to absorb knowledge, but to construct and use it in an autonomous way in varied and complex communication situations.

V. RESEARCH METHOD

Concerning our research methodology, this project follows the action research approach, which is characterized by the combination of the common contributions of theory and practice. Action research generally starts from a problem identified in the field and anticipates action through theoretical research by creating a network of didactic, pedagogical and technological conditions to create potential learning areas and find new solutions. It confronts knowledge and action to better theorize them.

In this perspective, we will begin by analyzing the current situation. We will first seek to respond to the issues raised by the integration of ICT in the teaching of French in the qualifying secondary cycle. We will then articulate the added value of their integration in the French course, while highlighting concrete examples that do not restrict teachers' creativity.

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